

DIHYDROKURCHINE.

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Kurchine was isolated from the bark of *Halarrhaena antidysenterica* by Ghosh and Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 477). In the course of an examination of the bark of this tree (Peacock and Chowdhury, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 734) we isolated kurchine and several other alkaloids. We tried to reduce these in ethyl alcohol solution by Adams, platinum oxide method; with conessine (Haines, *Pharm. J.*, 1865, ii, 6, 432) lettocine (Peacock and Chowdhury, *loc. cit.*), isoconessimine (Siddiqui, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 283) and conimine (Siddiqui, *loc. cit.*); no reduction was observed. Kurchine ($C_{23}H_{38}N_2$) gave dihydrokurchine ($C_{23}H_{40}N_2$) as an oil which could not be obtained crystalline. Dihydrokurchine gave a dihydriodide ($C_{23}H_{40}N_2 \cdot 2HI$), m.p. 212°, a neutral sulphate ($C_{23}H_{40}N_2 \cdot H_2SO_4$), very sparingly soluble in water, m.p. 334° and a picrate, m.p. 176°. Kurchine itself was not acetylated by heating with acetic anhydride but dihydrokurchine gave an acetyl compound [$C_{23}H_{39}N_2 \cdot (COCH_3)$], m.p. 112°. It would appear, therefore, that of the two tertiary nitrogen atoms in kurchine one is combined as $>C : N-$ and on reduction gives $>CH-NH-$. Dihydrokurchine gave a nitroso derivative ($C_{23}H_{39}N_2 \cdot NO$), m.p. 109°, and a *p*-toluenesulphonyl derivative ($C_{23}H_{39}N_2 \cdot SO_2C_6H_4Me$), m.p. 174°. Dihydrokurchine is thus a secondary base.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Dihydrokurchine.—Kurchine (1.3 g.) was mixed with platinum oxide (0.05 g.) and rectified spirit (36 c.c.) and shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen for 1½ hours at 28-30°. Reduction then appeared complete, the volume of hydrogen absorbed was 135 c.c. corresponding approximately to the addition of one molecule. The solution was filtered from platinum, acidified with hydrochloric acid and the ethyl alcohol removed under reduced pressure. The residue was dissolved in water and a solution of sodium sulphate

added, when the sparingly soluble dihydrokurchine sulphate was precipitated. It was recrystallised from rectified spirit in colourless needles, m.p. 334° (decomp.). (Found: SO_4 , 21.1, 21.7. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{49}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires SO_4 , 21.7 per cent). The base liberated from the sulphate was a colourless oil soluble in acetone, ether, petrol ether, benzene and chloroform.

Dihydrokurchine Hydriodide.—It was precipitated as an oil by adding a strong solution of potassium iodide to a solution of the hydrochloride of the base. It crystallised from hot water as colourless prisms, m.p. 222°, sparingly soluble in cold water, readily soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohol. (Found: I, 42.07, 42.1. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{49}\text{N}_2\text{I}_2$ requires I, 42.3 per cent). *Dihydrokurchine picrate* crystallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 176°.

When lettocine, conessine, *isoconessimine* and *conimine* were similarly treated no reduction was observed.

Acetyldihydrokurchine.—Dihydrokurchine (0.2 g.) was mixed with anhydrous sodium acetate (0.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 c.c.) and heated for 3 hours on an oil-bath at 135–140°. The acetic anhydride was removed under reduced pressure and the residue dissolved in water, basified with ammonia and extracted with ether. The ether was removed when an oil was obtained which is readily soluble in acetone, methyl alcohol, ethyl acetate and benzene; sparingly soluble in petrol ether. It was dissolved in methyl alcohol and neutralised with dilute sulphuric acid. The acetyl dihydrokurchine sulphate crystallised on cooling as colourless needles from hot water, m.p. 268°. [Found: SO_4 , 10.93, 10.91. $(\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{49}\text{ON}_2)_2$, H_2SO_4 requires SO_4 , 11.0 per cent]. The base, liberated from the sulphate by caustic soda, was taken up in ether, the ether removed and the residue repeatedly crystallised from rectified spirit when it was obtained as colourless needles, m.p. 112°.

Kurchine similarly treated was not acetylated.

Nitrosodihydrokurchine.—Dihydrokurchine (0.8 g.) was dissolved in 10% acetic acid (15 c.c.), cooled and a solution of sodium nitrite (0.5 g.) in water (5 c.c.) slowly added. The nitroso compound which separated was filtered, washed with water and repeatedly crystallised from rectified spirit. *Nitrosodihydrokurchine* separated as pale yellow crystals, m.p. 109°, sparingly soluble in ether, petrol ether and ethyl acetate; soluble in acetone, acetic acid and ethyl alcohol. (Found: N, 11.0. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{39}\text{ON}_3$ requires N, 11.26 per cent).

p-Toluenesulphonyldihydrokurchine.—Dihydrokurchine (0.8 g.) was mixed with 10% caustic soda solution (10 c.c.) and finely powdered

p-toluenesulphonyl chloride (10 g.) slowly added with good shaking. After 2 hours the mixture was heated to 80° to decompose unchanged sulphonyl chloride, filtered and washed. The oily crude product was repeatedly precipitated from rectified spirit and finally obtained crystalline. *p*-Toluenesulphonyldihydrokurchine is readily soluble in acetone, ethyl acetate and chloroform; sparingly soluble in ether and petrol ether, m.p. 174°. (Found: S, 6.23. $C_{30}H_{46}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 6.43 per cent).

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